

Visit Intention to Urban Tourism: The Impact of Destination Image and E-WOM Using Visitor Behavior as a Mediating Variable

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Abstract:- How to get more visitors to a particular urban tourist location and encourage return trips is a crucial problem. The PIK tourist spot area has developed into a popular urban tourism trend because to its culinary, distinctive, and intriguing picture places. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of Destination Image and E-WOM Using Visitor Behavior as a Mediating Variable on Intention to visit Urban Tourism. Quantitative research techniques are employed to provide more thorough, valid, trustworthy, and objective data. The sample consists of 247 visitors who visited three tourist attraction in the PIK district of North Jakarta, namely Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran PIK, and Urban Farm. The data were processed and analyzed using SEM-PLS (Partial Least Squares) technique after going through the relevant stages. The results of the study showed that the impact of Destination Image and E-WOM Using Visitor Behavior as a Mediating Variable has a positive impact on Visit Intention

Keywords:- Visit Intention, Urban Tourism, Destination Image, E-WOM, Visitor Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourist business has grown so quickly, many nations now view it as a crucial component of their overall economic development. In fact, tourism is the largest industry in the world from the standpoint of global development. Many nations view a thriving industry as a key driver of economic growth, field work, the private sector, and infrastructure development (Abadi, Soleimani, Shabgoomonsef, & Afrooz, 2021). Tourism activities generate demand, both in terms of consumption and investment, which leads to the production of goods and services.

In 2020, there were significant economic changes in the travel and tourism industry, and the Covid-19 pandemic issue had a significant impact on the industry globally. Many governments in the world, including the Government of Indonesia, have taken policies to anticipate the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, including stay at home, lockdown and large-scale-social-restriction (Rahmanita, Nurbaeti, Asmaniati, Dewi, & Widyastuti, 2021). The Covid-19 outbreak has all but destroyed Indonesia's travel and tourist sector (Hamsal & Abdinagoro, 2021). When operating, the tourism industry also consists of several closely related enterprises. Other industries are impacted when Covid-19

disrupts this industry. Tourism growth is beginning to squirm. Many domestic tourists have begun to visit several tourist attractions. Domestic tourism can be the backbone of the tourism industry's recovery after the Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has caused almost every aspect of consumer behavior to shift in order to accommodate the new normal (Machdar & Andreas, 2021). Outdoor locations are preferred by customers over indoor locations. To survive and thrive, business actors in the tourism industry must be able to quickly adapt to normal "disruption." In this case, PIK managers respond to consumer demand for shared open spaces by becoming a creative forum and encouraging visitors to participate in collaborative and healthy activities. Visitors can enjoy delicious food in the middle of the plantation, or enjoy the aesthetic atmosphere of the open space, and take interesting photos to upload to social media during the day while enjoying the outdoors. The management promotes North Jakarta's PIK neighborhood as a desirable urban and culinary tourism destination.

The urban tourism development is an attempt to increase local revenue through restaurant and hotel taxes while also increasing economic activity in the city (Utama, 2015). For a variety of rational and responsible reasons, both scientific and non-scientific, urban tourism development will be the promised future developed in Indonesia. The city's targeted trend is the subject of development attention, which also includes the growth of the tourism industry. Because educated people predominate in metropolitan regions, urban citizens are able to easily embrace the most recent issues relating to modernization and economic empowerment. The number of cities, however, periodically rises as a result of the regional development tendency.

Tourism development is one type of tourism that is valued. Tourism will continue to grow as people's lifestyles change, making tourism a trend. Tourism potential in Indonesia is very important, both as a potential for urban tourism with many urban centers and as a potential for urban tourism and attractions in urban areas. One critical issue is how to attract more people to a specific urban tourism destination, resulting in repeat visits. Because of its culinary, unique, and interesting photo spots, the PIK tourist spot area has become a viral urban tourism trend. As a result, the study was carried out to determine whether the destination image and E-WOM factors can influence visitors' decisions to visit the location.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Urban Tourism

Urban tourism as a collection of tourist resources or activities situated in cities that are made available to visitors from other locations (Klingner, 2006). This concept may thus be described as follows: urban tourism is a generic type of tourism that uses urban features (not agricultural) and all aspects of city life (service centers and economic activities) as tourist attractions. Urban or urban districts become one of the key components in a region's infrastructure and economic growth. The idea of urban tourism is beginning to evolve and be utilized to assist excellent city development. Urban tourism includes activities performed by both domestic and foreign tourists as well as by city dwellers, and is framed by constructed and natural environments, facilities, and infrastructure. Urban regions, such as towns and cities, serve as gates to other locations, serve as tourist sites, and are sources of travelers (Cave & Jolliffe, 2012)

B. Destination Image

Destination image is an interactive system of ideas, feelings, attitudes, visualizations and intentions towards a destination (Gartner & Cavusgil, 2007; (Tasci, et al. 2021). This description includes cognitive, affective, and perspective aspects of the image, expressing ideas and views about a place that evoke feelings and emotions, which influence behavior towards that location. However, the conative aspect of the image becomes irrelevant in studies that also include other behavioral variables, such as destination loyalty or its dimensions. Several studies have investigated and amplified the impact of destination image on different behaviors before, during, and after visiting a place (Coban 2012; Kim, Styliadis and Oh 2019; Kislali, Kavaratzis and Saren 2019; Tasci & Gartner, 2007; Wang & Hsu, 2010). This study often uses cognitive and affective aspects. Attractions, climate, and facilities are primarily place-oriented aspects of destination image (Tasci, et al. 2021).

Destination image can be considered as the perception of tourists and sellers of the available attributes or attractions (Hallmann, Zehrer, & Muller, 2015). The destination image is inherent in the destination and is critical in explaining, advertising, integrating, and distributing destination products. As a result, numerous academics have discovered that the concept of image is crucial for comprehending how tourists choose their destinations (Pike, 2002; Jeong & Holland, 2012). The image is a critical component in the promotion of tourism destinations because what distinguishes one destination from another is critical to its success (Carballo, et al. 2015; Acocer dan Ruiz 2019). The perception of a destination image is made up of two parts: the value linked to the inner destination with motivation, and beliefs and knowledge about the outcomes of the evaluation of features and benefits in the form of affective elements (Pratminingsih, Rudatin dan Rimenta 2014; Dagustani, et al. 2018).

C. e-WOM

One method for influencing their location's reputation as a shopping and tourist destination is through e-WOM and WOM (Martini, et al. 2022). Word of mouth (WOM) and electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) both influence consumer behavior and purchase decisions (Bartosik-Purgat, 2018; Badir & Andjarwati, 2020; Kajtazi & Zeqiri, 2020; Martini, et al. 2022). EWOM and WOM play an important role in business promotion, particularly in the tourism industry. When people and organizations communicate about a product or business online or through the Internet, this is known as electronic word of mouth, or e-WOM (Siang, Yang, & Liu, 2020). Electronic word-of-mouth is a means of communication that allows people who have never met or known one another to exchange information about a good or service they have used (Gruen, Osmonbekov, & Czaplewski, 2006). Three dimensions of electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) were positively reflected (1) numerous consumer opinions posted on social networking sites add intensity to eWoM: access to information from social networking sites on a regular basis, the frequency with which users of social networking sites interact with one another, the number of reviews written by social networking site users; (2) Value of Opinions: Consumers' good or negative opinions about brands, products, and services. Two characteristics of the value of opinion are both negative and positive. Positive recommendations from social networking site users and complaints from those same individuals are valued opinions; (3) Social networking sites' content refers to the information they provide about goods and services. Information about the quality (taste, texture, and temperature) of the food and beverage, as well as information on the pricing offered, are indicators of content (Goyette, et al. 2010).

D. Visitor Behaviour

Visitor behavior refers to the activities that visitors do in reaction to anything they do. Stimulating visitors to act can be split into two categories: internal stimuli (internal) and external stimuli (external) (Morrison, 2018). Internal stimuli, individual visitor elements such as: style of thinking, manner of perception, material conditions, economic conditions, gender, and so on frequently produce internal incitement. External stimuli are often created by circumstances, friends, relatives, and destination marketing operations.

Consumer behavior is influenced by a variety of factors, which are classified as (1) psychological: motivation, perception, learning, beliefs, and attitudes; (2) personal: age and life-cycle stage, occupation, economic circumstances, lifestyle, personality, and self concept; (3) social: reference groups, family, roles, and status; and (4) cultural: culture, subculture, social class system (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018). Consumer behavior determines how product information is found and evaluated (Solomon, 2019). Consumer behavior is a key factor in product purchases, even if it cannot be controlled. Therefore, it's crucial to pay attention to customer behavior (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018)

E. Visit Intention

Consumers have goals or behaviors to be achieved in solving problem or being satisfied with a decision (Firmansyah, 2018). There are five major stages in the consumer decision-making process: problem detection, information search, alternative evaluation and selection, outlet selection and purchase, and post-purchase procedures (Morrison, 2018).

When visitor feel the desire to engage in tourist activities, the purchase process begins. These requirements are often triggered by one or more stimuli, both internal and external. When someone decides they need to travel, they often begin researching the places, things, and services that they think would fulfill that desire. The prospective visitor examines options or choices based on the information that comes to mind after obtaining the necessary information. This stage demonstrates how a person's ideas and/or feelings might affect his or her decisions. Some people make purchasing decisions based on their objective, logical thinking, while others base their decisions on their feelings (subjective criteria). Someone chooses to come because they are determined or intend to schedule a visit immediately without preparation. However, the purpose is not always unanimous and might be swayed by other variables, such as discussions with family members, friends, or other interpersonal sources. To be sure, social media networks may be reviewed again to confirm the selections that have been made. The typical behavior of visitors is to evaluate their time at the location after having eaten there. The assessment procedure is often completed on the drive home or right after they get home. They will compare what they have received to what they expected previously. If their expectations are fulfilled or surpassed, they are more likely to be happy with the destination, to remember and share their experiences on social media, to tell others about their experiences, and to recommend friends, family, or others to visit the location.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study takes a quantitative method, gathering data from visitors who visited three tourist attractions in the PIK district of North Jakarta, namely Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran Chinatown, and Urban Farm. If the sample size was obtained using multivariate (correlation or multiple regression), the sample size should be at least 10 times the number of variables assessed (Sugiyono, 2020). The sample size for this study was 247 respondents. A digital questionnaire was distributed to respondents directly using a google form utilizing the probability sampling approach, which uses basic random sampling to collect data. The questionnaire has 39 question items separated into five sections: socio-demographic, visit intention, destination image, E-WOM, and visitor behaviour using a Likert scale of 1 (very unsatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied). After the data is obtained, it is processed using SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square). PLS is a version-based element of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). PLS-SEM was developed in two phases to evaluate the research design. First, the external model (measurement) is tested for reliability and validity, including the evaluation of indicator reliability,

internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. Second, the internal (structural) design is evaluated, and the hypothesis is tested (Hair, Jr., et al. 2017). The research hypotheses include:

- H₁: Destination Image has impact on Visitor Behavior
- H₂: E-WOM has impact on Visitor Behavior
- H₃: Visitor Behavior has impact on Visit Intention
- H₄: Destination Image has direct impact on Visit Intention
- H₅: E-WOM has direct impact on Visit Intention
- H₆: Visitor Behavior mediates the positive impact of Destination image on Visit intention
- H₇: Visitor Behavior mediates the positive impact of E-WOM on Visit Intention

A. Data Collection

The study data comprised of both primary and secondary sources. The current study used both qualitative and quantitative data. The data was gathered from both primary and secondary sources. The information was gathered through library and outdoor research (observation, direct interview, questionnaire, and documentation). This research's data was gathered through observations, interviews, library research, and documentation. The data were analyzed using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) technique after going through the relevant stages.

The sample size for the research is based on the specifications for the multivariate (correlation or multiple regression analysis), which calls for 247 samples. All visitors to Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran Chinatown, and Urban Farm were included in the research's population. The sample consists of 247 respondents who were chosen using the non-probability sampling method of purposive selection, which enables the researcher to choose respondents without providing equal opportunity to all segments of the population.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondent Demographic Characteristics

In Table 1 depicts the respondents' demographic characteristics of respondents. Male respondents made up 43.3 percent of the sample while females made up 56.7 percent. This shows that females are more consumptive in visiting to Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran PIK, and Urban Farm. The respondents are dominant aged 34 – 41 years (19.4 percent) with education of 44.9 percent are bachelor graduates and this explains that visitors who visit to Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran PIK, and Urban Farm are of productive age. Most of the consumers are from West Jakarta area (23.1 percent). The characteristics of the occupation 48.6 percent are private employed, and 22.3 percent are student. From this data, visitors who visit are dominated by private employed and students. Income of respondent is known that 24.7 percent has an income of < IDR 3,000,000, 22.7 percent of IDR 3,000,000 – IDR 6,000,000, and 19.4 percent of IDR 6,000,000 – IDR 10,000,000. This shows that visitors who visit at Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran PIK, and Urban Farm the average income is middle to above. They are usually sensitive to prices and comparisons with prices of other location, so that in determining the price of culinary at Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran PIK, and Urban Farm must be careful and with an

in-depth study, with the loyalty of visitors who visit at these places will be maintained. The characteristics of frequently visit, it is known that first time (41.7 percent) and second – three time (38.1 percent), and four - five time 11.3 percent. It shows that visitors who visit to these places are loyal visitors. To keep the first comer to be loyal visitors, Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran Chinatown, and Urban Farm can provide special prices of culinary and always innovate so as not to be abandoned by loyal visitors. Considerations for visiting these places with families, the data obtained are 56.3 percent, visiting with friends is 22.7 percent, and visiting with partner is 13.8 percent. This shows that visitors choose these places because of its culinary, unique, and interesting photo spots,

and very suitable for young families, friends and couple. Visitors can select more than one location, as well as the location of the most popular tourist attractions are dominant Pantjoran PIK (72.2 percent of 247 respondent), Cove at Batavia PIK are 63.1 percent of 247 respondent, and Urban Farm are 44.8 percent of 247 respondent. The selection of many social media platforms that are frequently used to find information about attractions in PIK are dominant Instagram (76.2 percent of 247 respondent), Tiktok are 31 percent of 247 respondent, You Tube are 27.8 percent of 247 respondent, and facebook are 20.2 of 247 respondent. This shows that many visitors to find information about Cove at Batavia PIK, Pantjoran PIK, and Urban Farm via Instagram.

Characteristics Respondent	Category	F	%
Gender	Male	107	43.3
	Female	140	56.7
Age	< 18	10	4.0
	18 – 25	79	32
	26 – 33	44	17.8
	34 – 41	48	19.4
	42 – 49	35	14.2
	>49	31	12.6
Occupation	Government Employed	2	0.8
	Private Employed	120	48.6
	Entrepreneur	20	8.1
	Students	8	3.2
	Students College	55	22.3
	Others	42	17
Education	Junior High School	5	2.0
	Senior High School	56	22.7
	Diploma	54	21.9
	Bachelor	111	44.9
	Postgraduate	19	7.7
	Doctoral	2	0.8
Monthly Income	<IDR 3 milllion	61	24.7
	IDR 3 – 6 million	56	22.7
	IDR 6 – 10 million	48	19.4
	IDR 10 – 15 million	24	9.7
	>15 million	26	10.5
	Others	32	13
Time of Visit	Weekday (Monday – Thursday)	40	16.2
	Weekend (Friday – Sunday)	207	83.8
Frequently Visit	First Time	103	41.7
	2 – 3 times	94	38.1
	4 – 5 times	28	11.3
	6 – 10 times	12	4.9
	>10 times	10	4.0
	Residential Area	Bekasi	17
Bogor		46	18.6
Depok		16	6.5
West Jakarta		57	23.1
Central Jakarta		5	2.0
South jakarta		26	10.5
East Jakarta		13	5.3
North Jakarta		25	10.1
Tangerang		32	13.0
Others		10	4.0

Considerations visiting with	Partner	34	13.8
	Tour Group	6	2.4
	Family	139	56.3
	Alone	12	4.9
	Friends	56	22.7
Spot Location	Cove at Batavia	159	63.1
	Pantjoran PIK	182	72.2
	Urban Farm	113	44.8
Media Source	Twitter	14	5.6
	Instagram	192	76.2
	YouTube	70	27.8
	Facebook	51	20.2
	Tiktok	78	31
	Travel Blogs/Website	34	13.5

Table 1:- Demographic Characteristics
Sources: The Processed Primary Data (2022)

B. Model for Test Measurement

The outer model was assessed for reliability and reflective validity of the learnt idea in accordance with the output of the PLS algorithm (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011). As shown in Table 2, all loading indicators (which only range in value from 0.555 to 0.835) are greater than the 0.50 upper limit suggested by (Chin, 1998; (Hartono & Abdillah, 2014; Anuraga, Sulistiyawan, & Munadhiroh, 2017) the range of 0.5 to 0.60 is deemed sufficient for the initial research stage of constructing a measuring scale for the outer loading value, at which point the indicator is deemed to be valid. When evaluating the internal consistency and reliability of multiple-item scales, Cronbach's coefficient alpha is utilized. Because each item in this study was testing an underlying concept, Cronbach's alpha was employed. Alpha coefficients of 0.6 to 0.7 imply a tolerable degree of dependability, and 0.8 or higher a very good level, according to a generally recognized guideline (Hulin, Netemeyer, & Cudeck, 2001; Ha, 2020). If

the alpha coefficient is more than 0.60, it is therefore considered to be statistically valid and reliable. All four measurement indicators were found to be valid and reliable. Cronbach alpha > 0.6, with values ranging from 0.839 to 0.937 and improving internal consistency reliability in result study, the composite reliability (CR) values ranged between 0.899 and 0.945, which was higher than the necessary 0.70, indicating that all indicators will be used in testing the research hypothesis. In a multiple linear regression model, multicollinearity is defined as a significant correlation or link between two or more independent variables. Tolerance and Variance Inflating Factor (VIF) values may be found here. There is multicollinearity if the Tolerance value is 0.1 and the VIF is more than 10 (Amalia, 2018). All VIF with values ranging from 2.354 to 2.805 < 10, there is no multicollinearity in the resultant model since three independent variables result in a VIF value of less than 10.

Item/Construct	OL	CR	α	VIFs
Destination Image (X₁)		0.899	0.871	2.354
Visit to Spot location worthwhile (culinary, unique and interesting photo spots)	0.697			
Easy access to Spot Location.	0.671			
Availability of online public transportation facilities in Spot area.	0.602			
In Pantjoran PIK, there are Chinese ornaments with an architectural style full of philosophy, distinctive hues, and inspiration for tourism and education.	0.727			
The atmosphere of Singapore, with spectacular coastline views at Cove of Batavia, contributes to PIK's distinctiveness and attractiveness.	0.757			
Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm as Urban Tourism.	0.796			
Feel that all urban tourism-related activities at the PIK Tourist Spot area have been efficiently managed.	0.774			
Feel that the management has fulfilled its role in developing tourism development in the community	0.777			
E-WOM (X₂)		0.919	0.901	2.768
Frequently use social networking platforms to find tourist information on PIK.	0.702			
On social networking sites, I frequently connect with other customers about PIK Tourist Spot information.	0.712			
Users of social networking sites have submitted several evaluations regarding PIK tourist attractions.	0.742			
interested in visiting the PIK Tourist Spot because of the many positive comments written by social media users on Twitter, Facebook and other social media.	0.804			

Interested in visiting PIK tourist attractions due of social media suggestions.	0.801			
Do not visit tourist attractions if there are no recommendations on social media.	0.596			
Utilize social media to learn about the selection of foods and beverages, as well as the costs, that Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm provide.	0.749			
Utilize social media to get trustworthy details on the flavor, texture, and temperature of the food and beverages served at Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm.	0.835			
PIK Tourist Sites information gives a nice setting with Chinatown style, Singapore mood, coastal vistas, and numerous instagramable spots via social media.	0.774			
Visitor Behavior (X₃)		0.875	0.839	2.805
Visit the PIK Tourist Spot, which has become a viral urban tourist trend due to its culinary, unique and interesting photo spots.	0.555			
Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm offer a variety of culinary and other services at reasonable prices.	0.640			
Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm offer products and services that meet their demands, leaving customers delighted.	0.763			
Other products and services at PIK Tourist Spots are well-organized and easily accessible.	0.659			
Urban tourism at the PIK Tourist Spot has extra qualities that distinguish it from other urban tourism outside the PIK region.	0.697			
Purchasing products at PIK Tourist Spots frequently results in discounts.	0.603			
Visiting PIK tourist attractions because friends or relatives have persuaded them.	0.575			
Knowing about the well-known urban tourism destinations Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm	0.732			
Cove at Batavia, Urban Farm, and Pantjoran PIK made me pleased to travel since they met visitor demands for healing and culinary pursuits.	0.715			
Visit Intention (Y)		0.945	0.937	
Spot locations were visited because of the location and pricing supplied in accordance with the visitor's preferences.	0.756			
More interested in seeing Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm among the various tourist sites available.	0.794			
Find out about spot locations after seeing advertisements on social media.	0.685			
Learn about Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm from friends or family.	0.671			
Visitors may easily obtain review information about spot locations via social media.	0.636			
Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm provide more appealing price discounts and facilities than other urban tourism.	0.793			
Knowing the benefits in terms of cost, distinctiveness, and environment, compared to other urban attractions in Jakarta, visitor choose to go to this spot locations.	0.827			
In comparison to other urban tourism in Jakarta, the availability of varied culinary establishments, unique and intriguing photo sites with gorgeous landscape.	0.724			
Visitors choose Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm because the facilities, rates, services, and availability are all satisfactory.	0.811			
Visitors are certain that choosing to come to Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm is the best decision.	0.807			
The PIK region is a tourism destination that caters to visitors' demands.	0.763			
Visitors are satisfied and will make a repeat visit to Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, Urban Farm	0.781			
Visitors will recommend to friends/relatives that Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, Urban Farm have the advantages of good urban tourism	0.746			

Note: OL = Outer Loading, CR = Composite Reliability, α = Cronbach's Alpha, VIF = Variance Inflation Factor

Table 2:- Measurement Model

Sources: The Processed Primary Data (2022)

C. Testing Direct Effect and Testing Indirect Effect

The coefficient of determination describes how much variation or behavior of the independent variable may be explained by the variation or behavior of the dependent variable.

R Square	R Square Adjusted
0.780	0.778

Table 3:- Visit Intention to Urban Tourism: The Impact of Destination Image and E-WOM Using Visitor Behavior as a Mediating Variable

Sources: The Processed Primary Data (2022)

As shown in Table 3, the processed results for the visit intention model obtained an adjusted R Square value of 0.778, which indicates that the variation or behavior of the independent variables (destination image, E-WOM, and visitor behavior) is able to explain the variation of the variation of the dependent variable (visit intention) to a degree of 77.8 percent; the remaining 22.2 percent is the variation of other independent variables that affect visit intention but are not included in the model. The external model is stated to be valid and can be adopted based on the preceding findings. The following phase is to examine deep models and hypotheses. In table 4. demonstrates that the suggested theory's findings are directly supported by each of the five hypotheses. The findings show that all estimates are positive, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$, and the p value 1 tail is $< \alpha = 1\%$ significance level. The conclusions 5 hypotheses of the proposed theory are accepted.

Destination Image on Visitor Behavior in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > T_{table}$ was

obtained: $7.505 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that the destination image has a direct relationship with visitor behavior. So it can be concluded that the destination image has a significant influence on visitor behavior. These results indicate that there are impact of destination image on different behaviors before, during, and after visiting a place (Coban 2012; Kim, Styliadis and Oh 2019; Kislali, Kavaratzis and Saren 2019; Tasci & Gartner, 2007; Wang & Hsu, 2010).

E-WOM on visitor behavior in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ was acquired: $6.729 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that E-WOM has a direct connection to visitor behavior. There are effects of E-WOM on visitor behavior which will then affect visitors' purchase intentions before making a decision to visit to Spot Location PIK and findings imply that disseminating information about spot location PIK by E-WOM might help visitor to have a favorable opinion of spot urban tourism PIK.

Hypotesis	Narration	Expected	Estimate	T Statistic	P Values 2 Tail	P Value 1 Tail	Result
H ₁	Destination Image -> Visitor Behavior	(+)	0.471	7.505	0.000	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted
H ₂	E-WOM -> Visitor Behavior	(+)	0.384	6.729	0.000	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted
H ₃	Visitor Behavior -> Visit Intention	(+)	0.276	3.745	0.000	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted
H ₄	Destination Image -> Visit Intention	(+)	0.302	5.001	0.000	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted
H ₅	E-WOM -> Visit Intention	(+)	0.387	5.276	0.000	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted

Note: * = alpha 10%, ** = alpha 5%, ***= alpha 1%

Table 4:- Hypothesis Testing Direct Effect

Sources: The Processed Primary Data (2022)

Visitor behavior on visit intention in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ was acquired: $3.745 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that visitor behavior has a direct impact to visit intention. These findings suggest that when visitor behavior increases, the decision to visit will increase, where the trend of urban tourism is viral because of the culinary, unique and interesting photo spots that are available at Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm makes visitor want to visit.

Destination image on Visit Intention in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ was acquired: $5.001 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that destination image

has a direct impact to visit intention. These results indicate that destination image is also a determining factor for potential visitor to visit urban tourism and as an individual's cognition of a destination, which includes an assessment of cognition, learning, perception, and feeling.

E-WOM on Visit Intention in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ was acquired: $5.276 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that E-WOM has a direct impact to visit intention. These results indicate that electronic word of mouth influences visitors' purchase decisions, in order for someone to readily trust in a product and make a buying choice through electronic word of mouth.

Fig 1:- PLS Regression Path

Two hypothesis testing indirect effect on Table 5 shown that mediator variable has positive impact to independent variable. The findings show that all estimates are positive, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$, and the p value 1 tail is $< \alpha = 1\%$ significance level. Visitor Behavior mediates destination image on visit intention in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ was acquired: $3.145 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that Visitor Behavior mediates the positive impact of destination image on visit intention. These results indicate that destination image which viral with culinary, unique and interesting photo spots available at PIK Pantjoran, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm can be change the behavior of

visitors from before, during and after visiting these location intend to visit again. The key factor of visitor intention to visit is the affective and cognitive tourist destination image. Similar findings show that destination image has a significant positive effect on tourists' visiting intentions (Satyarini, Rahmanita, & Setarnawat, 2017). The most significant effect on behavioral intention appears to be the destination vision (i.e., intention to review and willingness to recommend). There are two ways in which goal image impacts behavioral intentions: direct and indirect. Tourist destination image is made up of the outcomes of a rational evaluation or cognitive image and an emotive or affective image assessment (Tasci, Uslu, Styliadis, & Woosnam, 2021).

Hypotesis	Narration	Expected	Estimate	T Statistic	P Values 2 Tail	P Value 1 Tail	Result
H ₆	Destination Image -> Visitor Behavior -> Visit Intention	(+)	0.130	3.145	0.002	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted
H ₇	E-WOM -> Visitor Behavior -> Visit Intention	(+)	0.106	3.560	0.000	0.000***	Hypotesis Accepted

Note: * = alpha 10%, ** = alpha 5%, ***= alpha 1%

Table 5:- Hypotesis Testing Indirect Effect
Sources: The Processed Primary Data (2022)

Visitor Behavior mediates E-WOM on Visit Intention in Pantjoran PIK, Cove at Batavia, and Urban Farm, the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ was acquired: $3.560 > 2.345$ with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The positive t value indicates that visitor behavior mediates the positive impact of electronic worth of mouth on visit intention. These results indicate that visitors consider their decisions by looking at several decision items such as visiting because of various culinary places, unique and interesting photo sites with beautiful views obtained through e-wom. This is what encourages visitors to decide to visit a place. Changes from before and behavior before giving a very good response through EWOM can improve visitor visiting decisions (Utama and Giantari 2019). Through information and ideas obtained on social media, visitors may learn about the status of tourism goods such as rides, accessibility, and so on. This is to prevent making mistakes while deciding whether or not to visit a tourist attraction. Thus, the function of EWOM in information about anything may be considered to be the key to locating customers and changing visitor behavior in making decisions to visit a location.

V. CONCLUSION

The relationship between visitor behavior toward urban tourism, E-WOM toward urban tourism, destination image toward urban tourism, visitor behavior toward visit intentions toward urban tourism, and between destination image toward urban tourism and E-WOM toward urban tourism is one of positive impact on visit intentions toward urban tourism. In the meantime, visitor behavior mediates both the favorable effect of E-WOM and the favorable effect of destination image on visit intention. There are the identical replies with a reasonably modest scale of three variables from the indicators of questions presented to visitors (Visitor Behavior, E-WOM and Visit Intention). Only one variable, destination image receives the greatest score. Suggest to managers of Spot PIK locations should focus more on giving discounts and price promotions since purchasing items at spot PIK location seldom receives discounts and is less diversified, and some are not affordable for tourists who assume an average of IDR 3 million. It is hoped that by understanding the factors that influence the potential for urban tourism development in the PIK area as an urban tourism destination from the potential main attraction (destination image), the manager will be able to provide a variety of interesting events and entertainment that will attract visitors to return later in the day. The management must actively communicate with customers on social media and encourage new innovations, such as the installation of new picture places, the purchase of souvenirs, challenges, and intriguing things that entice visitor to return.

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